

What would be the estimated current/voltage to run the plate (ITO coated glass plate) to 36 °C. I am foreseeing Maximum Operating Temperature within the range 36 -39 °C.

Rishabh Sharma * , Shivam Sharma*

*Vritra Technologies, Address: 6, Malook Singh Marg Street No.-1, West Arjun Nagar, Delhi-110051, India, Email: info.vritratech@gmail.com, vritra@techie.com, URL: https://www.vritratech.com

Note these calculations are for:

Indium Doped Tin Oxide coated Glass (ITO) (100mm x 100mm)

- Sheet Resistance < 10 Ohm/sq
- Size: 100mm x 100mm
- Thickness: 1.1 mm

Electric resistance (R) of ITO sheet 100x100mm (sheet resistance < 10 Ohm/sq) is **45 Ohms** if electrodes are kept at the approximate distance of 100 mm

Now assuming the condition that surrounding temperature is 25 °C and temperature has to be increased to 36 °C. So temperature ΔT change is 11 °C which **284.15 Kelvin**.

Now, Electric power (P)

$$P = \frac{V^2}{R}$$

And Electric energy (E)

$$[E = P * t = \left(\frac{V^2}{R}\right) * t] \text{ --- (1)}$$

Assuming temperature change of 284.15 K is to be achieved in 60 seconds (So **time (t)= 60 sec**). And heat loss in surrounding is negligible or ideally Zero.

Specific heat (C_p) of ITO (90/10) is **330 J/kg.K**

And Density (d) of ITO (90/10) is **7.14 g/cc**

$$Cp = \frac{E}{m * T}$$

so,

$$[E = Cp * m * T] \text{ --- (2)}$$

here m is the mass of ITO film

$m = d * \text{Volume of ITO Film (which is around } 1.85 * 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^3)$

so **$m = 13.209 * 10^{-6} \text{ Kg}$**

Combining equation (1) and (2)

$$Cp * m * T = \frac{V^2}{R} * t$$

So,

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{Cp * m * T * R}{t}}$$

Putting all the values we get voltage of around 0.963 V. So you need 0.963 V to increase temperature by 11 °C in 60 sec, if electrodes are kept 100 mm apart.